

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF RAFT-FORMING FAMOTIDINE SUSPENSION FOR GERD

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ABSTRACT

Famotidine is an effective H₂ -receptor antagonist used in the management of GERD, but conventional formulations often do not provide immediate relief from symptoms like heartburn and acid regurgitation. This study describes the development of a raft-forming famotidine oral suspension containing alginate and gas-generating agents such as calcium carbonate and sodium bicarbonate, which form a low-density floating raft in acidic gastric conditions. The raft acts as a physical barrier to prevent reflux while enabling localized and sustained release of famotidine near the esophageal sphincter. Optimized parameters such as pH, viscosity, raft strength, and drug release ensure rapid symptom relief along with prolonged pharmacological action, making this formulation an effective dual-mechanism therapy for GERD.

KEYWORDS: Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease (GERD), Raft-Forming. Suspension, Famotidine, Floating oral suspension.

INTRODUCTION

Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease (GERD) is caused by backflow of gastric acid into the esophagus. Common symptoms include heartburn, acid regurgitation, chest discomfort, and throat irritation. Conventional tablets and capsules provide only temporary relief due to rapid gastric emptying. Frequent dosing reduces patient compliance.

Gastro-retentive drug delivery systems (GRDDS) increase gastric residence time. Raft-forming systems create a floating barrier to prevent acid reflux. Famotidine is an H₂ -receptor antagonist that reduces gastric acid secretion. Raft-forming famotidine suspension provides both immediate and sustained relief in GERD.^[1]

Approaches of Gastro-Retentive Drug Delivery Systems (GRDDS)

1. Floating Drug Delivery System:- Floats on gastric fluid due to low density. Types:-
 - a) Effervescent systems (gas-forming agents)
 - b) Non-effervescent systems (raft-forming polymers)
2. High-Density System:- Settles at the bottom of the stomach to resist emptying.
3. Modified Shape / Unfolding System:- Expands in the stomach to prevent passage into the intestine.
4. Bioadhesive System:- Adheres to gastric mucosa for prolonged retention.
5. Super-Porous Hydrogel System:- Swells rapidly to retain dosage form in stomach.
6. Magnetic System:- Retained in stomach using an external magnetic field.

Advantages of GRDDS

1. Improved drug absorption in stomach and upper intestine. Prolonged gastric residence time.
2. Controlled and sustained drug release.
3. Enhanced bioavailability.
4. Reduced dosing frequency.
5. Targeted drug delivery to stomach.
6. Reduced side effects.
7. Improved patient compliance.

Disadvantages of GRDDS

1. Not suitable for drugs unstable in acidic pH.
2. Requires sufficient gastric fluid and food.
3. Variable gastric emptying among patients.
4. Unsuitable for high-dose drugs.
5. Complex formulation and higher cost.
6. Risk of dose dumping.
7. Not suitable for patients with gastric motility disorders.(2)

RAFT-FORMING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

Raft-forming drug delivery system is mainly used in the treatment of acid reflux and related gastric disorders. After administration, the liquid formulation reacts with gastric acid to form a viscous, low-density gel or “raft” that floats on the stomach contents. This raft acts as a physical barrier between gastric acid and the esophagus, preventing reflux and providing rapid relief from heartburn. Trapped gas bubbles further improve buoyancy and prolong gastric retention.

Fig. 2: Raft-forming drug delivery system.^[3]

Potential

1. Provides a dual action: mechanical barrier (raft formation) and pharmacological effect (acid suppression). Suitable for management of GERD, gastritis, and peptic ulcer disease.
2. Increases gastric residence time, keeping the drug at the site of action for longer.
3. Prevents acid reflux by physically blocking the upward movement of gastric acid.
4. Ensures faster onset of action due to liquid formulation.
5. Reduces frequency of dosing because of prolonged effect.
6. Improves patient compliance, especially for patients with swallowing difficulty.
7. Provides immediate relief from heartburn and reflux symptoms.^[3]

FAMOTIDINE: A DRUG OVERVIEW

Famotidine is a competitive H_2 -receptor antagonist widely used in the treatment of acid-related gastrointestinal disorders. Introduced in the early 1980s, it suppresses both basal and stimulated gastric acid secretion by blocking H_2 receptors on gastric parietal cells, making it effective in GERD, peptic ulcer disease, and Zollinger–Ellison syndrome. Famotidine is valued for its high potency, long duration of action, minimal side effects, and low risk of drug interactions, as it does not inhibit cytochrome P450.^[6]

Chemical Formula:- $C_8H_{15}N_7O_2S_3$

Molecular Weight:- 337.5 g/mol

Appearance:- Appears as a white to pale yellow crystalline powder.

Solubility and classification:- Freely soluble in dimethylformamide & glacial acetic acid; slightly soluble in water and methanol. BCS Class III drug (poorly permeable, highly soluble).

Fig. 2: Structure of Famotidine.^[7]

Pharmacology:- Famotidine decreases stomach acid release by selectively inhibiting H₂ receptors on gastric parietal cells, leading to reduced acid secretion, less mucosal damage, and enhanced ulcer healing. Compared to earlier H₂ antagonists, Famotidine is 20 times more potent than cimetidine and about 7.5 times more potent than ranitidine in inhibiting acid secretion. It shows higher potency and a prolonged effect lasting up to 10–12 hours without causing endocrine disturbances. The drug is safe for long-term therapy, available in both oral and parenteral dosage forms, and helps maintain gastric pH above 4, thereby effectively relieving symptoms such as heartburn, acid reflux, and epigastric discomfort while lowering the risk of ulcer recurrence.^[6]

Pharmacokinetic (ADME)

1. Absorption:- After oral administration, famotidine is rapidly but incompletely absorbed, with peak plasma concentration achieved within 1–3 hours. Its oral bioavailability is about 40–50%. Food does not significantly affect absorption, though antacids may reduce it. The onset of action occurs within one hour, making it effective for acute symptom relief.
2. Distribution:- Famotidine is widely distributed in the body with a volume of distribution of 1.0–1.3 L/kg and shows low plasma protein binding (15–22%). It can cross the placenta and is excreted in breast milk, so caution is advised during pregnancy and lactation.
3. Metabolism:- Famotidine undergoes minimal hepatic metabolism, with most of the drug remaining unchanged and only a small fraction converted to a sulfoxide metabolite. It does not inhibit cytochrome P450 enzymes, resulting in a low potential for drug–drug

interactions.

4. Excretion:- Famotidine is primarily eliminated via the kidneys, with about 70% excreted unchanged in urine. The elimination half-life is 2–4 hours in healthy individuals but may be prolonged in elderly patients and those with renal impairment, requiring dose adjustment. It is also eliminated through active tubular secretion.^[4]

Pharmacodynamics: - Famotidine reduces both resting and stimulated gastric acid secretion by blocking histamine action at H₂ receptors. It begins to act within one hour after oral administration, reaches peak effect in 1–3 hours, and provides acid suppression for 10–12 hours. Its blood levels closely relate to acid-reducing activity, helping maintain gastric pH above 4. Famotidine does not interfere with cardiovascular, renal, endocrine, or pancreatic functions, making it suitable for long-term therapy.^[5]

FORMULATION COMPONENTS AND EXCIPIENTS

The raft-forming famotidine suspension is prepared using suitable polymers, gas- generating agents, Preservatives, sweeteners, and flavoring agents. The choice of excipients ensures proper gelation, Floating behavior, stability, and patient acceptability.

Table 1: Key excipients and their Functions.^[2]

Components	Examples	Functions
Polymers	Sodium alginate, xanthan gum, HPMC.	Gel formation, viscosity enhancement, raft strength
Gas generating agents	Sodium bicarbonate, Calcium carbonate.	CO ₂ release for buoyancy
Cross linkers	Calcium chloride.	Improves gel strength and stability
Buffers	Tri sodium citrate.	Maintains pH stability
Preservatives	Methyl paraben and propyl paraben.	Prevents microbial growth
Sweeteners and flavours	Sucralose, Mint, Lime.	Improves taste and patient compliance

METHODOLOGY AND EVALUATION PARAMETERS

The study involves preformulating evaluation of famotidine and evaluation of the raft-forming suspension. Preformulation confirms drug identity and compatibility, while evaluation checks raft behaviour, drug content, and release profile.

Preformulation Studies

- Organoleptic properties (appearance, color, odor)
- Melting point determination (purity check)

- UV spectroscopy and λ_{max} identification
- Calibration curve for famotidine in 0.1N HCl.^[12]

Evaluation Parameters

- Physical appearance and color of suspension
- pH measurement at 37°C, Swelling index and density measurement.
- Viscosity using Brookfield viscometer
- Floating lag time (time to raft formation), In vitro drug release study using USP Type II dissolution apparatus.
- Floating duration (how long raft stays afloat)
- Gel strength measurement, Drug content determination (UV at 279 nm).^[13]

Future scope

GRDDS show strong future potential in overcoming the limitations of conventional dosage forms, especially for drugs absorbed in the upper gastrointestinal tract. These systems help improve bioavailability, provide prolonged drug release, enable targeted drug delivery to specific regions of the stomach, and reduce side effects by localized action. GRDDS can also enhance patient compliance through convenient dosage forms. Raft systems further improve drug performance by maintaining consistent drug levels and providing prolonged therapeutic effects, highlighting the need for continued research and development in this area.

CONCLUSION

This project focused on developing a raft-forming famotidine suspension for the management of GERD to provide prolonged gastric retention and improved symptom relief. The formulation formed a stable floating raft in gastric fluid, helping retain the drug at the site of action and reducing acid reflux into the oesophagus. Evaluation parameters such as pH, viscosity, drug content, floating behavior, and drug release were within acceptable limits. Overall, the formulation shows promising potential as an effective and patient-friendly alternative to conventional famotidine liquids, with scope for further clinical evaluation.

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